

Isoflavonoids from *Iris kumaonensis*[†]

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From the methanol extract of *Iris kumaonensis* four known isoflavones and one known isoflavone glycoside were isolated for the first time. Their structures were elucidated by spectral studies including 2D NMR analysis.

Iris kumaonensis Wall ex. Don. V. Lhatham (Iridaceae) is a perennial herb growing wild in western Himalaya from Kashmir to Uttaranchal at an altitude of 2500–4000 m. Rhizomes of this plant are used for fever¹ and roots are used for kidney infection². Genus *Iris* consists of about three hundred species and is distributed throughout the world. About twelve species are found in India². *Iris* species are known to be rich in isoflavones, flavones³ and quinones⁴. These classes of compounds have attracted considerable attention because of their antioxidant⁵ and cytotoxic⁶ properties. Two isoflavones iridin and iriskumonin⁷ have previously been reported from the rhizomes of *I. kumaonensis*. Earlier we also reported⁴ six new alkylated benzoquinones, irisoquin-A, irisoquin-B, irisoquin-C, irisoquin-D, irisoquin-E, irisoquin-F and a known benzoquinone from the hexane extract of *I. kumaonensis*. During our ongoing research for characterization and identification of new secondary metabolites from western Himalayan flora, we now report 5,4'-dihydroxy-6,3'-dimethoxyisoflavones, 5,7,4'-trihydroxy-6,3'-dimethoxyisoflavone (iristectorigenin-A), 5,4'-dihydroxy-6-methoxyisoflavone-7-O-β-D-glucopyranoside (tectoridin), 5,7-dihydroxy-6,3',4'-trimethoxyisoflavone and 5-hydroxy, 6,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyisoflavone, isolated from the methanol extract of this plant. These are reported here for the first time from *Iris kumaonensis*. The identification of these compounds was carried out by spectral analysis (IR, MS, 1D and 2D NMR). Tectoridin was further confirmed by its hydrolysis and comparing the hydrolysis products with authentic samples.

Compound 1 (15.2 mg), m.p. 150–151°C was identified as 5,4'-dihydroxy-6,3'-dimethoxyisoflavone by comparison of its spectral data with the reported values⁸.

Compound 2 (17.5 mg), m.p. 163.7–163.8°C was iden-

tified as 5,7,4'-trihydroxy-6,3'-dimethoxyisoflavone (iristectorigenin-A), from its physical data and by comparison of its spectral data with literature⁸.

Compound 3 (35.4 mg), m.p. 261.8–263.2°C was identified as tectorigenin-7-O-β-D-glucopyranoside (tectoridin)⁹. Hydrolysis of this compound with 5% HCl in methanol afforded the flavonoid tectoregenin and sugar. Sugar part was confirmed as glucose by its co-TLC with an authentic sample and aglycone part was identified as tectorigenin by comparison of its spectral data³ and also by comparison with an authentic sample.

Compound 4, m.p. 188–190°C (32 mg) was identified as 5,7-dihydroxy, 6,3',4'-trimethoxyisoflavone. The structure was assigned on the basis of spectral studies and by comparison of its spectra with literature data¹⁰.

Compound 5, m.p. 236.2–238.0°C (43 mg) was identified as 5-hydroxy, 6,7,3',4'-tetramethoxyisoflavone. The structure was assigned on the basis of spectral and chemical studies and by comparison of its literature data¹⁰.

	R ₁	R ₂	R ₃
1	H	OMe	OH
2	OH	OMe	OH
3	OGlu	OH	H
4	OH	OMe	OMe
5	OMe	OMe	OMe

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These compounds are being reported for the first time from *I. kumaonensis*. Their 2D NMR (^1H - ^1H COSY, HMQC, HMBC) spectra were analysed to confirm their structures. NMR values based on 2D techniques of all compounds are given in the experimental section.

Experimental

NMR spectra were recorded in $\text{CDCl}_3/\text{CD}_3\text{OD}/\text{DMSO-}d_6$ on Bruker DRX 300 instrument using TMS as internal standard; IR spectra were measured on a JASCO FT/IR 5300. EIMS were recorded on Finnigan Mat 900 S mass spectrometer.

The rhizomes of *I. kumaonensis* were collected from Jalori Pass, Kullu district at 3500 m altitude in Himachal Pradesh, India during October 1999. An authenticated voucher specimen (No. 452 VKK) has been deposited in the herbarium section of the Institute.

Fresh rhizomes (1 kg) were cut in to small pieces and extracted with n-hexane, followed by CHCl_3 . The marc left after CHCl_3 extraction was further extracted with MeOH, and 80 g of the extract was obtained. 40 g of this crude MeOH extract was chromatographed over silica gel G (800 g) using pure chloroform. Fractions 1-3 did not show presence of any compound and subsequent fractions 4-12 were eluted with CHCl_3 : MeOH (99 : 1). From fractions 4-12 compound **1**, 15.2 mg was isolated, which showed a single spot on TLC plate run in CHCl_3 : MeOH (98 : 2). On repeated chromatography on silica gel using CHCl_3 : MeOH (96 : 4) afforded compound **2**, iristectorin-A (17.5 mg) and purified after crystallization in MeOH. Again the fraction eluted in CHCl_3 : MeOH (85 : 15) gave compound **3** (35.4 mg) analysed for $\text{C}_{22}\text{H}_{22}\text{O}_{11}$. ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, $\text{DMSO-}d_6$) δ 157 (C-2), 121.8 (C-3), 181.4 (C-4), 153.3 (C-5), 131.0 (C-6), 151.2 (C-7), 94.7 (C-8), 153.6 (C-9), 107.3 (C-10), 121.8 (C-1'), 116.0 (C-2'), 157.2 (C-3'), 116.0 (C-4'), 131.0 (C-5'), 133.1 (C-6'), 61.2 (6-OMe), 100.8 (Glu-C-1''), 73.8 (C-2''), 77.2 (C-3''), 69.0 (C-4''), 77.8 (C-5''), 60.7 (C-6''). Further rechromatography on silica gel of fractions 7-14 with CHCl_3 : EtOAc (97 : 3) afforded compound **4** which showed a single spot on TLC plate CHCl_3 : EtOAc : Me_2CO (96 : 3.5 : 0.5) analysed for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_7$. ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 - d_1) δ 153.3 (C-2), 120.0 (C-3), 181.6 (C-4), 153.4 (C-5), 130.9 (C-6), 153.4 (C-7), 93.6 (C-8), 155.5 (C-9),

106.8 (C-10), 124.1 (C-1'), 115.2 (C-2'), 146.0 (C-3'), 147.2 (C-4'), 111.0 (C-5'), 123.4 (C-6'), 61.2 (6-OMe), 56.4 (4'-OMe). Further running the column with CHCl_3 : EtOAc (95 : 5) and crystallised with chilled MeOH yielded another single compound **5** (43.0 mg) analysed for $\text{C}_{19}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_8$. ^{13}C NMR (300 MHz, CDCl_3 - d_1) δ 153.8 (C-2), 123.4 (C-3), 181.8 (C-4), 155.5 (C-5), 130.7 (C-6), 156.3 (C-7), 93.8 (C-8), 152.9 (C-9), 106.0 (C-10), 122.0 (C-1'), 115.1 (C-2'), 145.6 (C-3'), 146.0 (C-4'), 110.7 (C-5'), 130.3 (C-6'), 61.3 (6-OMe), 60.8 (7-OMe), 56.4 (3'-OMe), 56.3 (4'-OMe).

Hydrolysis of compound 3 : 25 mg of compound **3** was dissolved in 50 ml of 5% HCl in MeOH, refluxed for three hours and monitored by TLC. After complete hydrolysis it was partitioned by EtOAc. The organic layer containing aglycone part was concentrated and chromatographed to get tectorigenin and aqueous part containing sugar was concentrated to a residue which was identified as glucose by Co-TLC with an authentic sample.

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